

FORCED VIBRATION ANALYSIS AND OPTIMIZATION OF MODERATELY-THICK FIBER STEERED LAMINATES WITH EMBEDDED GAPS AND OVERLAPS

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ABSTRACT

Fiber placement is an automated manufacturing process that enables the steering of carbon fibers along preferable curvilinear paths. If optimized, steered fibers impregnated with epoxy resin can provide a significant improvement in the static and dynamic behaviour of a composite part. The manufacturing process, however, is far from being defect free. In particular, gaps and overlaps often appear during the placement of the fibers, with a resulting impact on the structural responses of the manufactured laminates. Such an impact on the variable stiffness properties has been recently assessed in literature for thin laminated structures. For fiber steered thick structural parts, however, the impact of gaps and overlaps is unknown. In addition, recently the use of Automated Fiber Placement (AFP) has been extended to manufacture moderately-thick composites, especially for applications as manned submersibles and wind turbine blades. This paper focuses on moderately-thick fiber steered laminated plates and aims at studying the role of shear deformation on forced vibration responses of fiber steered composite plates with embedded gaps and overlaps. To reduce the computational effort for the structural analysis, we use the equivalent single-layer method. In addition, to account for transverse shear stresses, we resort to third-order shear deformation theory, which assumes a quadratic distribution of transverse shear strain/stress through the thickness. Semi-analytic solutions are derived for the forced vibration analysis, using the hybrid Fourier-Galerkin method along with a numerical time integration technique. The effects of manufacturing parameters and transverse shear stresses are examined for a rectangular laminated plate under undamped vibration. Formulated in a multi-objective optimization framework, the optimum design of a variable stiffness plate is obtained to simultaneously maximize the vibration frequency response as well as the out-of-plane and in-plane stiffness.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced composites have a wide range of applications from aerospace to biomedical industries [1], due to their high strength/stiffness-to-weight ratio, fatigue strength, and resistance to corrosion [2, 3]. Laminated fiber-reinforced composites are conventionally fabricated by stacking laminae of straight fibers, which exhibit the highest strength in the fiber direction and the lowest strength in the direction transverse to fibers. The advent of Automated Fiber Placement (AFP), an advanced composite manufacturing technology, has industrialized the manufacturing of variable stiffness composites by steering fiber-tows along curvilinear paths within the lamina. The fiber-steered laminates have been shown to outperform straight-fiber laminates in improving the structural performance, such as the reduction of stress concentration [4], enhancement of the buckling load [5, 6], and the maximization of fundamental frequency [7].

AFP machines place a band of tows (course) on a mould. The discrete changes of the course width by adding or dropping an individual tow, result in emerging defects in the form of gaps and overlaps. There are a few studies which focus on the effect of this manufacturing defects on structural properties of steered-fibers laminates. Among them, “Defect layer method” [6] is capable to efficiently model the stiffness matrices of fiber-steered composites with embedded defects. This method is adopted in this paper.

A fully detailed three-dimensional (3D) analysis of laminated composites requires computationally expensive numerical procedures to solve the governing equations. Equivalent single layer (ESL) approach reduces the 3D problem to a two-dimensional (2D) problem by appropriate postulations for the kinematic of deformation and the stress state through the thickness of laminates [2]. The classical laminated plate theory (CLPT), first-order shear deformation theory (FSDT), and third-order shear deformation theory (TSDT) are a few examples of the ESL approach [3]. As opposed to CLPT, TSDT relaxes the kinematic assumptions on the straightness and normality of a transverse normal after deformation. In addition, TSDT does not need to use the FSDT shear correction factor, which is cumbersome to be determined for composite structures. As a result, TSDT have been applied to structural analysis of constant stiffness composites [8], functionally graded materials [9, 10], and fiber-steered composites [3].

There is an extensive number of applications where fiber-reinforced composites are used as the skin of sandwich structures [11]. Recently, there is a growing interest for using variable stiffness composites as the skin in a sandwich panel such as a stowed solar array wing. In the sandwich panel design, localized bending, buckling, and wrinkling of the skins could be determined by considering the skins as plates or shells resting on an elastic foundation provided by the sandwich core [12]. The Winkler and Pasternak elastic foundation approaches are widely used for sandwiches with a flexible and compressible core to simplify the computational simulation of the structural analysis of sandwich panels.

In this paper, we turn our attention to the forced vibration analysis of fiber-steered laminated composite plates with embedded manufacturing defects. We develop formulations using TSDT for composites resting on a Pasternak elastic foundation. The effects of manufacturing parameters, transverse shear stresses, and elastic foundation on the undamped vibration responses are examined. Finally, the optimum design of a variable stiffness plate is obtained to simultaneously maximize the vibration frequency response as well as the out-of-plane and in-plane stiffness.

2 GENERAL SPECIFICATIONS

To design a variable stiffness laminate, it is necessary to define a reference path along which the AFP machine places the first course. Subsequent fiber paths are then obtained by shifting the reference path along a given direction, e.g., x - or y -directions. A complex mathematic function for reference fiber path offers high flexibility for laminate tailoring; this, however, comes at the cost of a larger number of the design variables defining the fiber path. In addition, highly curved paths modeled with a complex function might not be necessarily manufacturable by AFP due to the violation of a minimum turning radius constraint. In this study, we consider a constant curvature fiber path with a trajectory given by [3]

$$\cos \theta = \cos T_0 + \frac{|x|}{R}, \quad R = \left| \frac{a/2}{[\cos(T_1) - \cos(T_0)]} \right| \quad (1)$$

where θ represents the fiber orientation along the fiber path, T_0 is the fiber orientation at the plate center, T_1 is the fiber orientation at the plate edges, R is the turning radius, and $|\dots|$ denotes the absolute value. Curvature k of the fiber path is also defined as: $k = 1/R$. As a result, a single layer may be represented by $\langle T_0 | T_1 \rangle$, where $T_0 = T_1$ represents a straight fiber. The shifting direction of the reference fiber path, affecting both fiber angle and defect distribution, plays a major role on the performance of a variable stiffness design. For instance, Fig. 1 depicts the effect of shifting direction on the fiber angle and gap distribution within a $\langle 45 | 26 \rangle$ design.

Fig. 1 Gap (shaded area) distribution: (a) fibers shifted along y -direction and (b) fibers shifted along x -direction.

3 PROBLEM DEFINITION AND GOVERNING EQUATIONS

We consider a rectangular variable stiffness plate and investigate the effect of fiber-steered composites, manufacturing defects, and elastic foundations on linear forced-vibration responses. Length, width, and total thickness of the considered plate are represented by a , b , and h , respectively (Fig. 2). The composite plate is rested on a Pasternak elastic foundation with Winkler spring stiffness k_w and shear layer stiffness k_s . The composite plate is subjected to a dynamic distributed transverse load $q(x, y, t)$, which is applied in an step-function fashion, for the forced-vibration analysis.

Fig. 2. Geometry of a rectangular laminated plate with a curvilinear fiber path.

To accurately predict the kinetic behavior of moderately-thick variable stiffness plates, the displacement field, along coordinate axes, is expressed using TSDT [2]:

$$\begin{aligned}
 u(x, y, z, t) &= u_0(x, y, t) + z\varphi_x(x, y, t) - c_1 z^3 \left(\varphi_x(x, y, t) + \frac{\partial w_0(x, y, t)}{\partial x} \right) \\
 v(x, y, z, t) &= v_0(x, y, t) + z\varphi_y(x, y, t) - c_1 z^3 \left(\varphi_y(x, y, t) + \frac{\partial w_0(x, y, t)}{\partial y} \right) \\
 w(x, y, z, t) &= w_0(x, y, t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where (u_0, v_0, w_0) represents the displacement components of the midplane ($z = 0$). Moreover, φ_x and φ_y stand for rotations about y - and x -axes, t represents time, and $c_1 = \frac{4}{3h^2}$ ($c_2 = 3c_1$).

The TSDT equations of motion of a plate rested on Pasternak elastic foundation could be derived by the principle of virtual displacement as [13]:

$$\begin{aligned}
 N_{xx,x} + N_{xy,y} &= I_0 \ddot{u}_o + J_1 \ddot{\varphi}_x - c_1 I_3 \ddot{w}_{0,x} \\
 N_{xy,x} + N_{yy,y} &= I_0 \ddot{v}_o + J_1 \ddot{\varphi}_y - c_1 I_3 \ddot{w}_{0,y}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \bar{Q}_{x,x} + \bar{Q}_{y,y} + c_1(P_{xx,xx} + 2P_{xy,xy} + P_{yy,yy}) + q(x, y, t) - k_w w_0 + k_s (w_{0,xx} + w_{0,yy}) \\
& = I_0 \ddot{w}_o - c_1^2 I_6 (\ddot{w}_{0,xx} + \ddot{w}_{0,yy}) + c_1 (I_3 (\ddot{u}_{0,x} + \ddot{v}_{0,y}) + J_4 (\ddot{\phi}_{x,x} + \ddot{\phi}_{y,y})) \\
& \quad \bar{M}_{xx,x} + \bar{M}_{xy,y} - \bar{Q}_x = J_1 \ddot{u}_o + K_2 \ddot{\phi}_x - c_1 J_4 \ddot{w}_{0,x} \\
& \quad \bar{M}_{xy,x} + \bar{M}_{yy,y} - \bar{Q}_y = J_1 \ddot{v}_o + K_2 \ddot{\phi}_y - c_1 J_4 \ddot{w}_{0,y}
\end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
(N_{\alpha\beta}, M_{\alpha\beta}, P_{\alpha\beta}) &= \int_{-\frac{h}{2}-h_M}^{\frac{h}{2}+h_M} \sigma_{\alpha\beta}(1, z, z^3) dz, \quad (Q_\alpha, R_\alpha) = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}-h_M}^{\frac{h}{2}+h_M} \sigma_{\alpha z}(1, z^2) dz, \quad \bar{M}_{\alpha\beta} = M_{\alpha\beta} - c_1 P_{\alpha\beta} \\
\bar{Q}_\alpha &= Q_\alpha - c_2 R_\alpha, \quad I_i = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}-h_M}^{\frac{h}{2}+h_M} \rho z^i dz, \quad J_i = I_i - c_1 I_{i+2}, \quad K_2 = I_2 - 2c_1 I_4 + c_1^2 I_6 \\
& \quad (\alpha, \beta = x, y) \quad (i = 0, 1, \dots, 6) \tag{4}
\end{aligned}$$

where $\sigma_{\alpha\beta}$ and ρ are, respectively, the stress components and mass density; the superposed dot on a variable stands for the time derivation.

4 METHODOLOGY

In contrast to constant stiffness composites, stiffness matrices of fiber-steered composites with curvilinear fibers are a function of spatial coordinates (x, y) . As a result, developing closed-form solutions for structural responses of variable stiffness composites is cumbersome, even for simply-supported boundary conditions. Therefore, a semi-analytic methodology using the Fourier-Galerkin method, introduced in [3], is adopted in this paper for the simply-supported boundary condition (SS-1).

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we focus on the undamped forced-vibration responses and we examine the effect of manufacturing strategies, elastic foundation, and fiber orientation for variable stiffness plates with the length-to-thickness ratio of $a/h=10$. A 16-ply balanced and symmetric laminate with $[\pm < 58 | 39 >]_{4s}$ layup is chosen to validate the developed methodology with numerical results reported in [3].

Figure 3 shows the undamped temporal deflection at the plate midpoint, where the maximum out-of-plane deflection of the fiber-steered plate occurs. It can be seen that the panel made by a complete-gap strategy have a higher amplitude of dynamic deflection and a lower response frequency compared to a defect-free case, while a complete overlap strategy leads to a lower amplitude of deflection and a higher frequency. For example, deflection amplitude is increased by 9% and the frequency is decreased by 3% for a plate with gaps compared to a defect-free plate, while the deflection amplitude is decreased by 24% and the frequency is increased by 10% for a plate with overlaps. We recall the morphology of manufacturing defects as the reason of their effects on dynamic responses. Gaps are resin-rich areas with lower stiffness, while overlaps are thickness build-ups with improved flexural stiffness.

Fig. 3. Dynamic out-of-plane deflection at the center of the plate for alternative manufacturing strategies.

Figure 4 shows how an elastic foundation plays a role on the undamped temporal deflection. A defect-free variable stiffness plate, with applied dynamic load and geometries identical to those assumed in Fig. 3, is considered. The time evolution of the midpoint out-of-plane deflection is plotted for alternative elastic foundation stiffness. The dynamic responses are compared for four alternative elastic foundations: $(K_w, K_s) = (0, 0)$ (Unconstrained), $(K_w, K_s) = (50, 0)$ (Winkler foundation), $(K_w, K_s) = (0, 5)$ (Shear layer foundation), and $(K_w, K_s) = (50, 5)$ (Pasternak foundation). The presence of elastic foundation, caused by the compressible support of core material in sandwich applications of composites, decreases the amplitude of dynamic out-of-plane deflection and increases the dynamic frequency responses due to the increased stiffness of the structure.

Fig. 4. Dynamic out-of-plane deflection at the center of a variable stiffness plate for alternative elastic foundations.

To determine the optimum fiber path trajectory for a desired dynamic response, a multi-objective optimization routine is implemented. In this work, the minimization of amplitude of undamped out-of-plane dynamic deflection (w), maximization of undamped dynamic frequency (ω), and maximization of in-plane stiffness (E_{eq}) are considered as objective functions. The goal here is to find the fiber path parameters that minimize w and maximize ω and E_{eq} . The optimization problem is:

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}} \left\{ w(\mathbf{x}), \frac{1}{\omega(\mathbf{x})}, \frac{1}{E_{eq}(\mathbf{x})} \right\}; \mathbf{x} = (T_0, T_1)^T \quad (5)$$

$$s.t. \{ T_0, T_1 \in [0^\circ, 90^\circ] \& R \geq 25 \text{ in} \}$$

where \mathbf{x} represents the design variable vector, and R is the minimum turning radius of AFP. To reduce the computational cost involved in the optimization process, Radial Basis Function, as a surrogate model, is coupled with the non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm-II (NSGA-II) [5, 14].

Figure 5 illustrates the Pareto optimal designs for out-of-plane deflection versus in-plane stiffness (Fig. 5a) and dynamic frequency versus in-plane stiffness (Fig. 5b) each normalized by the value of their counterparts of a quasi-isotropic laminate with the following layup: $[45/0/-45/90]_{2s}$. As shown in Fig. 5, it can be seen that overlaps have a more pronounced impact on the laminate performance than gaps. As a result, considering the vibration behavior of a variable stiffness laminate, a complete overlap manufacturing strategy is more appropriate compared to a complete gap strategy.

Fig. 5 Pareto fronts for (a) normalized out-of-plane dynamic deflection and (b) normalized frequency versus the normalized in-plane stiffness.

6 CONCLUDING REMARKS

The effect of variable stiffness design and manufacturing defects on the vibration responses of fiber steered moderately-thick plates has been studied in this paper. We have adopted TSDT to account for the effect of transverse shear deformation. The forced-vibration analysis has been conducted and the application of elastic foundation on the undamped responses has been tested. Numerical results have shown that plates with gaps have a higher amplitude of dynamic deflection and a lower response frequency compared to a defect-free plate, as opposed to a plate with overlaps. The presence of elastic foundation applies external reactions to the composite structure that decreases the amplitude of dynamic out-of-plane deflection and increases the undamped dynamic frequency responses. The developed methodology in this paper could be used for the design of vibratory variable stiffness composite for sandwich panel applications.

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